

MULTISCALE MODELLING OF LAMINATION DEFECTS IN CURVED STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Finite element (FE) analysis of curved aerospace laminates has the potential to offset the cost of the expensive experimental testing that is required for certification. However, the number of degrees of freedom necessary to model entire parts (e.g. a wing spar) or to sufficiently resolve defects in smaller parts is extremely high. In order to solve these large problems efficiently a high level of parallelism is needed. For this reason a preconditioner suitable for large anisotropic problems has been implemented in the High Performance Computing library DUNE (Distributed and Unified Numerics Environment). GenEO coupled with an iterative solver such as CG can solve large problems quickly on hundreds of computer cores. This preconditioner can then be used to test the effect of varying the slope of a simple wrinkling defect on the initiation of damage. A convergence analysis of this example problem shows that models with fewer than 4 elements through-thickness in each ply and interface layer do not yield a good approximation of the stresses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Certification of large laminate aerospace parts, such as wing spars, currently relies on expensive experimental testing. This involves testing at all scales in the Test Pyramid, with large numbers of small coupon tests and fewer larger-scale structural tests. FE analysis has the potential to model entire component parts and to reduce conservatism. However, FE modelling of such materials is extremely challenging due to the huge aspect ratio between layer thickness and the size of the modelled structures, as well as due to the varying anisotropic material properties and the large contrast between fibrous and resin layers.

Modelling an entire airplane wing spar down to the scale of the layer thickness would require about 10^{10} degrees of freedom. In manufacturing small localised defects in the form of misaligned fibrous layers can occur, which require an even finer mesh resolution. Commercial FE tools, such as ABAQUS are typically

Figure 1: A CT scan of a simple wrinkle.

unable to model such components down to this level, mainly due to the direct linear equation solvers that are employed. For this reason a new general preconditioning strategy has been implemented in the High Performance Computing library DUNE [1, 2].

DUNE is an open source modular toolbox for solving partial differential equations with grid-based methods, such as the finite element method. Written using modern C++ programming techniques, the core modules of DUNE have been developed by mathematicians and computer scientists; to allow users to implement and use state-of-the-art mathematical methods across large high performance parallel computing architectures. DUNE is a generic package, and therefore provides the user with the key ingredients for solving any FE problem, e.g. grid generation, different types of finite elements, quadrature rules and a choice of off-the-shelf solvers.

DUNE is able to reproduce the results of standard FE libraries such as ABAQUS [5], with large reductions in solution times for models with large numbers of degrees of freedom. Moreover, the new iterative solver within DUNE shows almost optimal parallel efficiency on hundreds of computer cores. This allows for models with sufficiently fine meshes to resolve defects or to model entire aerospace components with high accuracy.

In this paper, this new FE tool is applied to narrow curved laminates, typically tested in the certification process of wing spars. One loading of particular interest is a corner unfolding, in which though thickness tensile loading acts to separate the layers as the corner radius is increased under bending loads. These stresses act in the weak resin-dominated direction of the laminate and can therefore lead to a limiting design case. The presence of mis-aligned fibres in the form of out-of-arc wrinkles can cause a significant reduction in strength, referred to in manufacturing as a knock-down factor.

Mukhopadhyay et al have modelled the effect of defects on compressive [8] and tensile [7] strength in flat laminates using 8-noded, solid elements and zero-thickness, 8-noded cohesive elements between plies. Damage modelling accounted for nonlinear shear in plies (in 1-2 and 1-3 directions), transverse matrix cracking, mixed mode delamination, tensile fibre fracture and fibre kinking. The finite element mesh had minimum size of 0.25 mm in the vicinity of wrinkles and towards laminate edges. The compressive strength predictions were in agreement to within 10% of experimental results and were able to pick up a mode switch from fibre failure to delamination when defect misalignment was above about 9° . In the tensile case it was noted that wrinkles act as local, through-thickness shear stress concentrators. For multidirectional laminates, the influence of the defect was exacerbated by edge effects.

In Section 2.2 the capability of the preconditioner GenEO to efficiently and robustly solving massive simulations of composite structures is demonstrated. In the example simulations presented in Section 3, the composite strength of pristine and defected corner radii are accurately predicted. The analysis assumes standard anisotropic 3D linear elasticity and the failure is accessed using a quadratic damage onset criterion [3]. This allows the results to be benchmarked against existing numerical results, given in Fletcher et al. [4]. Further, the importance of a simple defect in the form of a wrinkle of varying slope the knock-down associated for wide specimens is assessed. A sample CT scan of such a wrinkle and the parameterisation of the wrinkle using a sech $(\cdot)^2$ -function is shown in Figure 1.

2 MODELLING APPROACH

The following models have been implemented using the DUNE module, *dune-composites* which solves the linear anisotropic elasticity equations applicable for modelling composite structures. This module provides an interface to handle composite applications which includes stacking sequence, complex part geometry and complex boundary conditions such as multi-point constraints, or periodic boundary conditions. Further, a 20 node serendipity element suitable for comparison with the ABAQUS element C3D20R has been included.

The computational gains of *dune-composites* are a direct consequence of the use of fast and robust iterative solvers for the resulting large systems of linear equations

$$Ku = f, \tag{1}$$

where K is the global stiffness matrix, f is the load vector arising from the applied boundary conditions and u is the solution vector containing the displacement values at each node within the finite element mesh. There are also significant gains in the setup time due to the more efficient, problem-adapted data management.

Solvers for systems of linear algebraic equations can broadly be classified into direct and iterative ones. Direct solvers, based on matrix factorisation, are more universally applicable and more robust to ill-conditioning. Thus, they are typically the default in commercial FE packages, such as ABAQUS. However, the cost of the factorisation and the memory requirements can quickly become infeasibly high for large problems. Moreover, it is difficult to achieve good parallel efficiencies on large multicore computer architectures. Since they do not require any factorisations, iterative methods have the potential to scale optimally, both with respect to problem size and with respect to the number of processors in a parallel implementation, but that crucially depends on the 'conditioning' of the problem.

The conditioning is a property of the the global stiffness matrix K . We say that K is ill-conditioned, if the nodal displacements u are highly sensitive to rounding errors and to small changes in f . Generally, simulations of composite structures are ill-conditioned because of the strong heterogeneity and the often complex, non-grid aligned anisotropy of the material. The condition number of K , which is defined as the ratio of the largest and the smallest eigenvalue of K , grows roughly linearly with the size of the largest jump in the entries of the stiffness tensor from one finite element to an adjacent one. But the conditioning also worsens systematically, as the problem size N increases. This growth is typically of order $N^{3/2}$ in 3D problems. This growth affects the accuracy of the solution in direct solvers to some extent, but it has no effect on the computational cost.

A standard approach to improve the conditioning of such problems is to apply a preconditioner P , typi-

Figure 2: A cross section of the configuration.

Orthotropic fibrous layer	
E_{11}	162 GPa
E_{22}, E_{33}	10 GPa
G_{12}, G_{13}	5.2 GPa
G_{23}	3.5 GPa
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.35
ν_{23}	0.5
Isotropic interface layer	
E	10 GPa
ν	0.35

Table 1: Mechanical properties for the curved 12-ply laminate.

cally a cheap approximation of K^{-1} , to (1) and then to iteratively solve

$$PKu = Pf. \quad (2)$$

Finding a good preconditioner for composite applications is extremely challenging due to the huge aspect ratio between layer thickness and the size of the modelled structures, as well as due to the varying anisotropic material properties and the large contrast between fibrous and resin layers. To achieve robust scaling, a new general preconditioning strategy is necessary, this will be described in Section 2.2.

2.1 Model setup

The chosen geometry with a defect is shown in Figure 2, the setup allows easy comparison with [4]. In the following tests the width W is variable. The model has 10 mm long limbs L and the inner radius of the curved section R is 22 mm. The overall thickness T is 9.93 mm, where the ply layers are 0.24 mm thick and the resin interfaces are 0.015 mm thick. The mechanical properties for the ply material and the resin interfaces are given in Table 1. The fibre angles are given by the following stacking sequence

$$[[\mp 45/90/0]_2/[\mp 45]_2/90/\mp 45/90/0/\mp 45/0/\pm 45/0/90/\pm 45/90/[\pm 45]_2/[0/90/\pm 45]_2].$$

A multipoint constraint on the upper limb was modelled by applying a thin layer of very stiff material to the top edge of one of the limbs and applying a 9.58 kNmm/mm moment to that limb. All degrees of freedom are fixed on the remaining limb in the model. Second order serendipity elements (corresponding to the ABAQUS element C3D20R) are used in this model to avoid shear-locking.

Figure 3: Top: Decomposition of a mesh into several subdomains (Ω), showing an overlap of one element in each subdomain. Bottom: Low energy eigenmodes in a reference block consisting of one layer of resin (white) and two layers of plies (green: 90° , blue: -45° , red: 45°). From left to right: A reference domain, a zero energy mode (rotation), a low energy mode between two 90° plies and a low-energy twisting mode caused by 45° and -45° plies.

2.2 The GenEO Preconditioner

In this section the two-level overlapping Schwarz preconditioner GenEO from [10] is introduced. It leads to almost optimal scaling with respect to problem size and number of cores. For the coarse space construction, GENEO computes generalised eigenvectors of the local stiffness matrices on the overlapping subdomains and builds an approximate coarse space by combining the smallest energy eigenvectors on each subdomain via a partition of unity. This preconditioner has been proven to be robust for isotropic problems in [6, 10]. We will show that it gives good results also for anisotropic problems and that it scales well over thousands of cores allowing us to successfully tackle the large problems mentioned above.

The GenEO preconditioner is based on a domain decomposition. A domain decomposition method works by splitting the computational domain into smaller subdomains and iterating to coordinate the solution between adjacent subdomains. The GenEO preconditioner uses overlapping domains, i.e. the subdomains overlap by more than the interface. The problems on the subdomains are independent, which makes this method suitable for parallel computing. The GenEO preconditioner is then applied to an iterative method, in our case, the conjugate gradient method (CG) has been used. A decomposition of the domain Ω is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Scaling of DUNE for up to 512 cores. Solid lines are used for the problem with $2 \cdot 10^4$ degrees of freedom per core and dashed lines are used for the problem with 10^4 degree of freedom.

A coarse problem with only a few unknowns per subdomain is used to further coordinate the solution between the subdomains globally. The coarse problem is approximated by computing a few of the smallest energy eigenmodes on each overlapping subdomain (or core). Some of these low energy modes can be seen in Figure 3. These local modes are then combined to generate a global coarse problem using a partition of unity method. This approach has been shown to give very good coarse approximation to problems arising from highly heterogeneous materials [11] and therefore naturally leads to a robust preconditioner which scales well over multiple cores. Details of their specific implementation in *dune-composites* are given in [9].

The main advantages to using the GenEO preconditioner is its robustness in terms of number of subdomains. In the test of the following section the number of iterations of GenEO stayed constant at roughly 40. However, the setup time for GenEO is large and thus it only becomes the most efficient solver for large problems with many subdomains.

The performance of the preconditioner GenEO is examined on hundreds of cores. The restriction to shared-memory parallelism, paired with the growth of $N^{3/2}$ in computational cost and memory requirements, limit the scalability of the direct solvers significantly, making it essentially computationally infeasible to carry out a corresponding test.

The FE model used for these tests grows in size as the number of cores N_{cores} grows. There are two different test setups. For the first, larger problem 56 elements along the radius, $6N_{\text{cores}}$ across the width and 4 elements each in the resin and ply layers are used. For the second problem the number of elements through-thickness is halved, leaving only 2 elements in each resin and ply layer.

As the number of cores increases, the width of the laminate is also increased. This ensures that each core has to handle a similar amount of work. Thus, as the width of the part and the number of cores increases, the time taken for the calculation stays roughly constant. Figure 4 shows that the scaling in DUNE indeed continues to at least 512 cores, allowing larger tests while keeping close to constant run time per processor core.

3 DEFECT ANALYSIS

During the manufacturing process a number of defect types can arise, which can have a large effect on the strength of the materials. In this section the effect that varying the slope of a localised wrinkle with only one oscillation has on the strength of the curved laminate is investigated.

Note that the results in this section do not take into account thermal pre-stresses, which occur as a result of the high-temperature curing process and may be significant. However, the purpose of this paper is to illustrate the importance of efficient preconditioners to solve large problems that arise when modelling defects.

In these tests a fixed width W of 52 mm is used. The loading from the previous section is applied. Clearly, the boundary conditions and loading in a narrow specimen are very different from those of the full structure. For this reason we model using periodic boundary conditions at the free edge. This gives an approximation of the effect of the wrinkle in a very wide part and ensures that the boundary effects do not influence failure.

A defect is introduced into the geometry by starting with a mesh on a flat plate, then adding the wrinkle to the flat plate and finally transforming to the curved geometry. Let s, l and r be coordinates in the unperturbed, flat geometry. Note, that in the final curved geometry, s corresponds to an arc length, r is the radius through the part and l is the width across the part. The stresses are denoted by the same naming convention: arc length s around the curve, radius r through-thickness and width l across the laminate.

In the flat geometry the wrinkle is given by a perturbation in r , which depends on all three coordinates. The perturbed coordinates $(\hat{s}, \hat{r}, \hat{l})$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{s} &= s \\ \hat{l} &= l \\ \hat{r} &= r + f(s, l, r).\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

If the location at which the defect is largest is denoted by $(s_{\text{def}}, l_{\text{def}}, r_{\text{def}})$, the function f giving the perturbation is

$$f(s, l, r) = d \operatorname{sech} \left(\pi \frac{s - s_{\text{def}}}{\pi b_1} \right)^2 \operatorname{sech} \left(\pi \frac{r - r_{\text{def}}}{R b_2} \right)^2 \operatorname{sech} \left(\pi \frac{l - l_{\text{def}}}{W b_3} \right)^2,\tag{4}$$

where d gives the amplitude of the defect and $b_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ are parameters giving the ‘‘length’’ of the defect in the three directions.

For these tests b_2 is chosen so that the wrinkle decays more quickly towards the inner radius. More precisely,

$$b_2 = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } r - r_{\text{def}} < 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} & \text{if } r - r_{\text{def}} > 0 \end{cases}.$$

Further, $b_1 = \frac{1}{5}$ and $b_3 = \frac{1}{2}$.

The stresses in the vicinity of a wrinkle, including inter-laminar shear and direct stress. Therefore a mixed mode failure criterion is more suitable than a maximum stress criterion. The strength of the laminates was assessed using a quadratic damage onset criterion, defined by Camanho et al. [3] as

$$F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_r^+}{s_{33}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{rs}}{s_{13}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{rl}}{s_{13}} \right)^2}\tag{5}$$

Figure 5: Convergence plot for a pristine part and a part with a defect with maximum slope 18° , with labels giving the number of elements through-thickness per ply and interface layer.

with negative values of σ_r treated as zero and the allowables $s_{33} = 61$ MPa and $s_{13} = 97$ MPa.

Curved laminates subjected to corner unfolding are observed to fail by delamination of the plies [4]. Since this indicates failure occurs at the interface between plies, we apply the failure criterion only in the resin-rich interface zones and failure initiates when $F = 1$. Generally, the failure criterion is applicable in the local coordinates of the material, however since the interface zone is isotropic, a transformation is not required.

To ensure that the FE modelling is sufficiently accurate a convergence analysis is included. In Figure 5 we plot the relative error in the peak failure criterion given by equation (5) below. As an approximation to the exact solution we used the next refinement level of the FE model (136 elements along the radius, 60 across the width and 8 each in the resin and ply layers). For the refinement we have chosen (second to last point) the relative error has been reduced to around 1% for both the pristine model and for the model containing a defect.

The models used in this analysis increase the number of elements through thickness in each layer as follows: 1, 1, 2, 4, 6, 6, 8. The number of elements across the part and around the radius and limbs are increased simultaneously. Especially for a part with a defect, the number of elements through thickness is very important. With fewer than 4 elements the model does not yield a good approximation of the maximum failure criterion or of the stresses.

Having established the wrinkle defect model, we now investigate the effect of varying the wrinkle severity. Figure 6 shows the effect on the interlaminar shear and direct stresses with a wrinkle of maximum angle (slope) of 4° and 18° for which an opening/bending moment of 9.58 kN mm/mm is applied. The interlaminar shear maximises in the region of greatest slope, while the interlaminar direct stress maximises in the region of peak amplitude. These stresses are highly localised and cause a sharp rise in failure index through-thickness, as shown in Figure 7.

The pristine part is predicted to fail near the mid-thickness, where direct interlaminar stress maximises. With a wrinkle of slope 4° , there is a rise in failure index near the inner radius, however failure is still predicted to first occur near the mid-thickness (as per the pristine model). As the slope of the wrinkle is

Figure 6: Stresses τ_{rl} and σ_l for defect angle 4° , followed by stresses τ_{rl} and σ_l for defect angle 18° (bottom).

Figure 7: Through-thickness quadratic damage onset criterion at the center of each resin interface (with linear interpolation between resin interfaces). Values are calculated at mid-width along the angle of steepest slope (2.1° from the apex of the curve and at a distance r from the outer radius).

FEA (normalised): Periodic BC											
Defect slope (deg.)	max. disp. (mm)	location	interface (from inner radius)	max. failure crit. F	σ_l (MPa)	σ_s (MPa)	σ_r (MPa)	τ_{sl} (MPa)	τ_{rs} (MPa)	τ_{rl} (MPa)	M (kN)
0	3.99	Mid-width	16	1.00	33.76	34.90	61.00	0.19	0.02	-0.23	9.58 ¹
4	3.98	Mid-width	16	1.07	37.26	40.72	65.59	0.17	0.95	0.47	8.90
8	3.98	Mid-width	4	1.30	51.67	113.2	65.69	-8.75	6.50	71.05	7.34
12	3.98	Mid-width	4	1.65	45.41	117.4	79.94	-12.80	9.97	97.59	5.78
18	3.98	Mid-width	4	1.94	37.31	131.6	92.99	-17.37	14.91	116.4	4.92

¹ABAQUS result was 9.51 kN

Table 2: Effect of the defect slope on failure criterion F , the predicted moment of initiation of failure M and on the stresses.

increased, so failure index near the inner radius becomes higher than that near the mid-thickness. This is also indicated in Table 2, showing failure at interface 16 for pristine and 4° wrinkle models, and at interface 4 for greater slopes. For the most severe wrinkle of slope 18°, the failure index is almost double that of the pristine model, and hence strength is halved.

A summary of all models is shown in Table 2. As seen by the maximum recorded displacement, the overall stiffness of the curved laminate is not significantly affected by the inclusion of a wrinkle defect. This is because it is very small in comparison to the size of the whole laminate. However, it does significantly reduce strength, based on initiation of failure. When tested in isolation such specimens have been found to fail in a highly unstable manner, suggesting once initiation is reached there is instantaneous propagation and catastrophic failure [4].

Note that the pristine result in Table 2 compares well with predictions acquired by modelling the curved laminates using ABAQUS software; and Table 2 shows that the greatest impact of the wrinkle is to introduce significant interlaminar shear stresses.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Localized defects in the form of misaligned fibrous layers require a very fine mesh resolution to accurately model stresses. Current industry standard FE tools, such as ABAQUS, are not able to deal with these problem sizes, largely due to the direct linear equation solvers that are employed and due to the restricted parallel scalability. For this reason, a new preconditioner (GenEO) has been implemented in the library DUNE. Using this preconditioning scheme robust scaling up to hundreds of cores can be achieved. Care has to be taken though to guarantee robustness with respect to heterogeneities and anisotropies in the material properties. Black-box multilevel approaches do not scale indefinitely and more tailor-made solutions

are needed. The flexibility to prescribe or implement such tailor-made preconditioners is not available in commercial software, and therefore the development of codes like *dune-composites* are pivotal in solving large-scale problems in composite structures.

The chosen example problem evaluates the through-thickness stresses caused by unfolding a curved laminate with defects. This serves to illustrate the importance of using a high-fidelity mesh and provides insight into the influence of small manufacturing induced defects. For both the pristine part and a part with a small defect the number of elements through thickness is very important. Fewer than 4 elements through each layer do not achieve a good approximation of the stresses or of the maximum failure criterion.

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